

Mitsunobu coupling of 7-hydroxycoumarins with allylic and propargylic alcohols : A facile direct access to tertiary allyl coumarinyl ethers

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Allylic and propargylic alcohols are coupled with 7-hydroxycoumarins under Mitsunobu conditions using diethyl azodicarboxylate (DEAD) and triphenylphosphine to afford the corresponding coumarinyl ethers without any rearrangement in good-to-acceptable yields. This route provides direct access to the 1,1-dimethylallyloxy coumarins which are key intermediates for the Claisen rearrangement-based synthesis of linear and angular coumarins.

Coumarinyl ethers, particularly those derived from 7-hydroxycoumarins are fairly well represented in nature¹. Of these, the 3,3-dimethylallyloxy-, 1,1-dimethylallyloxy-coumarins and their oxidative variants are precursors to a large number of naturally occurring coumarins². These coumarins are also key intermediates for the Claisen rearrangement-based synthesis of linear and angular coumarins³ including pyrano- and furanocoumarins of photodynamic and diversified bioactivities. Very recently, 7-O-(3,3-dimethylallyl)coumarin and 1,1-dimethylallyl-coumarins are emerging as suppressants⁴ of lipopolysaccharide and interferon- γ -induced nitric oxide generation thereby counteracting diseases caused by it.

Allyl and propargyl ethers of coumarins are classically prepared by treating allylic and propargylic halides with hydroxycoumarins in refluxing acetone in the presence of

anhydrous potassium carbonate. This nucleophilic displacement reaction, however, excludes the preparation of 1,1-dimethylallyl ethers using 3-bromo-3-methylbut-1-ene because the undesired 3,3-dimethylallyl ether is formed as the predominant product by way of allylic rearrangement (S_N2'). A two-step sequence⁵ involving partial catalytic hydrogenation of the corresponding 1,1-dimethylpropargyl ethers with Lindlar's catalyst is the currently accepted protocol for the preparation of 1,1-dimethylallyl coumarinyl ethers. However, this methodology has serious drawbacks, e.g., 1,1-propargylic halides are strong lachrymators and environmentally hazardous; these are usually prepared from tertiary ethynylcarbinols which are often complicated by acetylene-allene rearrangements⁶ and even reduction of the propargylic ethers in the presence of Lindlar's catalyst is usually accompanied with some over-

Table 1. Mitsunobu coupling of 7-hydroxycoumarins with allylic and propargylic alcohols

Sl. no.	Hydroxycoumarin	Alcohol	Reaction time (h)	Mol. formula (yield ^a , %), [m.p., °C] ^b of coumarinyl ethers	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
					C	H
1.	1a	2a	20	3a, C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃ (78) [76°, lit. ¹¹ 77–78°]	72.96 (73.04)	5.98 (6.08)
2.	1a	2b	48	3b, C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₅ (62) [75–76°, lit. ⁵ 75–78°]	73.16 (73.04)	6.14 (6.08)
3.	1a	2c	36	3c, C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃ (74) [137–138°, lit. ⁵ 136–140°]	73.51 (73.68)	5.14 (5.26)
4.	1b	2a	15	3d, C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄ (75) [100–102°, lit. ⁵ 101–102°]	69.17 (69.23)	6.11 (6.15)
5.	1b	2b	48	3e, C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄ (64), oil	69.11 (69.23)	6.01 (6.15)
6.	1b	2c	36	3f, C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ (76) [140–142°, lit. ⁵ 140–144°]	69.57 (69.76)	5.28 (5.42)
7.	1c	2a	20	3g, C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ (73) [137–138°]	47.01 (47.19)	3.58 (3.65)

^aYields refer to chromatographically isolated pure products; the products are fully characterized by their spectral data (IR, NMR and MS) and these data satisfactorily agree with those published in the literature for compounds 3a-f. ^bM.p.s. were determined in a sulfuric acid bath and are uncorrected.

Scheme 1

reduction⁷. Although use of an activated form of 7-hydroxycoumarin on Amberlyst A26 support⁸ in the nucleophilic displacement of alkyl and allyl halides has been reported, no attempt has been made, to the best of our knowledge, to develop alternative procedure for the preparation of allyl coumarinyl ethers by direct coupling of allylic alcohols with hydroxycoumarins. Herein, we report a simple mild procedure of coupling of primary and tertiary allylic and propargylic alcohols with 7-hydroxycoumarins utilizing Mitsunobu reaction^{9,10} with diethyl azodicarboxylate (DEAD) and triphenylphosphine as the redox system (Scheme 1). The results of intermolecular condensation of these alcohols with hydroxycoumarins are summarized in Table 1.

3-Methylbut-2-enylation of 7-hydroxycoumarin (**1a**) and 7-hydroxy-5-methoxycoumarin (**1b**) with 3-methyl-2-buten-1-ol (**2a**) (entries 1,4) proceeded with ease and yields of the ethers were found to be comparable to those obtained with the corresponding alkyl halides^{5,11}. The presence of bulky *ortho*-substitution had no adverse effect on yield as shown by the coupling of 8-iodo-7-hydroxycoumarin (**1c**) with **2a**. With tertiary allylic alcohol 2-methyl-3-buten-2-ol (**2b**), however, the coupling of **1a** and **1b** were comparatively sluggish, as expected for the nucleophilic attack of hydroxycoumarins on a sterically hindered tertiary centre of phosphonium ion^{9b}. Importantly, these alkylations afforded 1,1-dimethyl allyl ether in acceptable yields without any allylic rearrangement. No *N*-hydrazine derivative was isolated. The yields of these tertiary coumarinyl ethers compared favourably with the overall yields of the same ethers by the partial reduction of the corresponding propargyl ethers (60.5% for **3b** and 71.8% for **3e**)⁵. Intermolecular condensation of **1a** and **1b** with 2-methyl-3-buten-2-ol (**2c**) led to the exclusive formation of 1,1-propargylethers **3c** and **3f** respectively in good yields without any acetylene-allene rearrangement. An obvious advantage of this methodology is that it does not require the additional step of conversion of

allylic and propargylic alcohols to the corresponding halides which is often prone to rearrangements, particularly for tertiary alcohols.

In summary, Mitsunobu coupling of primary and tertiary allylic and propargylic alcohols with 7-hydroxycoumarins has been executed under simple mild conditions in good-to-acceptable yields. This method allows direct preparation of *O*-1,1-dimethylallylcoumarins. In view of the wide occurrence of hydroxycoumarins in nature and commercial availability of the allylic and propargylic alcohols, this method holds promise of wide application for the synthesis of a variety of coumarinyl ethers.

Experimental

IR spectra (KBr/liquid film) were run on a Perkin-Elmer 1310 instrument and NMR spectra (CHCl₃) on Jeol FX100 (100 MHz) and Bruker AM-300L instruments with TMS as internal standard. Silica gel (60–120 mesh) was used for chromatographic purification and silica gel G (B.D.H.) for tlc experiments.

Mitsunobu coupling of allylic and propargylic alcohols with 7-hydroxycoumarins. Representative procedure : 7-Hydroxycoumarin (**1a**; 500 mg, 3 mmol) and 2-methyl-3-buten-2-ol (**2b**, 400 mg, ~4.6 mmol) were dissolved in dry tetrahydrofuran (25 ml) under nitrogen cover. To it was added triphenylphosphine (860 mg, 3.3 mmol) in two portions. The resulting mixture was stirred vigorously, and diethyl azodicarboxylate (580 mg, 3.3 mmol) in dry tetrahydrofuran (2 ml) was added dropwise over a period of 5 min at 0–5° when its orange-red colour disappeared immediately with substantial heating. The mixture was stirred for 48 h under nitrogen and then concentrated under reduced pressure. The concentrated mixture was then diluted with ether (20 ml) and the precipitated solid was filtered out. The filtrate, on concentration gave a solid which was chromatographed to afford 7-*O*-1,1-dimethylallylcoumarin (**3b**; 440 mg, 62%), m.p. 75–76° (chloroform-light petrol).

Characterization data for 8-iodo-7-O-(3,3-dimethylallyl)coumarin (3g) : ν_{\max} (KBr) 3000, 2980, 1720, 1600, 1290, 1240, 1150, 1060, 960, 825, 725 and 620 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.74, 1.71 (each 3H, s, 3'-Me₂), 4.62 (2H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz, OCH₂), 5.44 (1H, t, 2'-CH), 6.16 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz, H-3), 6.72 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, H-6), 7.34 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, H-5) and 7.51 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz, H-4); *m/z* (%) 356 (M⁺, 13.0), 288 (49.3), 287 (M⁺-C₅H₉, 100), 259 (*m/z* 287-CO, 22.4), 69 (C₅H₉⁺, 94).

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